

International Translation Studies from 1978 to 2022: A Bibliometric Analysis and Its Implications

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Abstract

This study conducts a bibliometric analysis of articles in 14 international translation journals indexed in SSCI or A&HCI from 1978 to 2022. It reveals diverse insights such as frequently explored topics, their evolution over five periods, highly-cited articles, productive and influential authors, and productive countries or regions. This study identifies important topics, such as translation technology, post-editing, machine translation, subtitling and audiovisual translation. It also demonstrates that emerging technologies and the cultural turn impact the field. Descriptive translation studies still influence current research. Additionally, the research reveals that interdisciplinary studies are gaining attention in translation studies. The study offers a comprehensive view but has some subjectivity in data analysis. Future research might improve validity with methods like surveys and interviews. It provides implications for the future direction of translation studies.

Keywords: translation studies; bibliometric analysis; frequently explored topics; research trends; implications.

1. Introduction

Translation studies is a discipline that focuses on the theories and practices of translation, interpreting, and localization. It has undergone substantial development in the past four decades, reflecting the changes in society, technology, and the way we communicate. In the past forty years, there has been an increasing amount of research on translation and interpreting employing various interdisciplinary approaches. For instance, the bibliometric approach has been applied in translation studies. However, most of these studies research only focus on certain aspects of translation studies. For instance, Akbari (2018) primarily concentrated on translation quality research based on 14 peer-reviewed journal articles during 2000-2017. Liu and Zhang (2019) conducted an analysis on healthcare interpreting studies using 40 journal articles between 2007 and 2017 from 23 A&HCI or SSCI journals. Rovira-Esteva, Olalla-Soler, and Aixelá (2020) focused on co-authorship in translation studies covering a time span of 56 years through BITRA online database. Rovira-Esteva, Aixelá, and Olalla-Soler (2021) conducted studies on open access citation advantage in translation studies, using data between 1996 and 2015 from Bibliography of Interpreting and Translation (BITRA) online database. Guo, Ang, and Xie (2023) conducted an analysis on translator's voice, covering a time span of 1996-2023 through Scopus and China National Knowledge Infrastructure online database. Pięta, Ivaska, and Gambier (2023) investigated indirect translation using data between 2017-2022 from a self-selecting database.

On the other hand, several other studies have placed a closer focus on the development and trends within the field of translation studies. For instance, Doorslaer and Gambier (2015) utilized the Translation Studies Bibliography (TSB) online database to examine the geographic distribution and five most frequently occurring keywords in selected journals. Zanettin, Saldanha, and Harding (2015) analyzed research interests and foci using data from the Translation Studies Abstracts (TSA) online database for the period between 1997 and 2011. Liang and Xu (2016) conducted an analysis of articles published from 2009 to 2013 in eight SSCI-indexed translation journals from the Web of Science online database, aiming to reveal developmental trends and the leading edge of translation studies. Huang and Liu (2019) examined the field of translation studies by analyzing articles published between 2014 and 2018 in 13 translation journals indexed in

SSCI or A&HCI, as retrieved from the Scopus online database. Pan and Wu (2024) examined the intellectual structures and research trends in the field of translation studies based on co-citation analysis and author-supplied keyword analysis of research articles in eleven SSCI-indexed translation studies journals from 2007 to 2021. Through these diverse approaches and different databases, these studies have contributed to a deeper understanding of the evolving nature of translation studies and its current research interests.

Although these studies are methodologically sound and thorough, they only focus on a certain field of translation studies or only focus on the development status of translation studies in the relatively short period, ignoring how translation studies have developed in the past 40 years, which could offer comprehensive implications for the development and limitations of translation studies. Moreover, except for Zanettin, Saldanha, and Harding (2015) identifying the hot research topic by extracting keywords from articles' abstracts, most previous studies examined hot topics through keywords from journals or authors' keywords, which may neglect some important key terms offered in articles' abstracts.

This study aims to identify the current trends and emerging areas of research interest in translation studies. It will analyze articles published in 14 translation journals between 1978 and 2022, which are indexed in the Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) or the Arts & Humanities Citation Index (A&HCI), using the Scopus online database to achieve a broader coverage and a more comprehensive overview. Additionally, a bibliometric approach involving quantitative analysis of publication and citation patterns will be used to determine the most frequently explored highly cited papers, influential authors and scholarly distribution. A corpus-based analysis will also be conducted to identify research topics. By adopting these methods, the study aims to map the current landscape of translation studies and highlight the latest developments and areas of focus. This research will contribute to a better understanding of the direction of translation studies and provide valuable insights for future research and scholarship in this area.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1 Data

All articles published in 14 international translation journals indexed in SSCI or A&HCI databases during 1978-2022 were collected from the database of Scopus as the basic corpus of this study, including Perspectives Studies In Translatology or Perspectives: Studies in Translation Theory And Practice, Translation Review, Babel, Target, Translator, Journal Of Specialised Translation, Meta, Translation Studies, The Interpreter and Translator Trainer, Interpreting, Linguistica Antverpiensia New Series-Themes in Translation Studies, Translation and Interpreting Studies, Across Languages and Cultures, Translation and Literature. The articles selected from these journals undergo peer-review and, more significantly, they represent the most influential and authoritative translation journals globally. The reason we collect data from Scopus instead of the Web of Science is that the bibliometric information of our selected journals, such as Translation Review, Babel, and Target, included in the Web of Science did not begin until 2010 or 2011, while the bibliometric information for these journals in Scopus began in 1973 or 1978.

The search statement we utilized is as follows:

TITLE-ABS-KEY ((translation) OR (interpreting) OR (interpreter) OR (translating) OR (translator)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")). The results were further refined by selecting the Scopus classification for "Arts and Humanities" and "Social Sciences". Source Title and document type of "article" of the above 14 international translation journals were selected, excluding book reviews, editorials, conference reports, erratum, letters to the reader and other journal items. Book reviews and reports are not the same as research papers in that they do not involve direct research. Using this data retrieval method, we collected 5512 original articles published between 1978 and 2022 in July 2023. Then we divided the entire 45 years into five periods: 1978-1988, 1989-1999, 2000-2010, 2011-2016, 2017-2022. The reason why we divided in this way is because of the comparability of the studies. As noted above, the data in 1978-1988, 1989-1999, 2000-2010 each covered 11 years, but the data in 2011-2016 and 2017-2022 each covered 6 years because since 2011, there has been a significant increase in translation studies papers due to the trend of globalization, the advancement of translation technology, the increase of cultural exchanges, and the attention of the academic community. It can be seen that the periods of 1978-1988, 1989-1999 and 2000-2010 have 179 items, 474 items and 1477 respectively, while the periods of 2011-2016 and 2017-2022 boast 1491 and 1902 respectively. Although the periods of 2011-2016 and 2017-2022 did not cover a full decade, the quantities of publications are more than eight times that of 1978-1988. Therefore, the way we split the time periods helps to make the number of items in the five time periods more comparable.

This article investigates the 1978-2022 bibliometric data of 14 international translation studies journals indexed in SSCI or A&HCI databases to explore the following research questions:

1. What have been the frequently-explored research topics in the over 45 years as well as in each of the divided periods (1978-1988, 1989-1999, 2000-2010, 2011-2016, 2017-2022)?
2. Which articles have been the most highly cited across the five periods?
3. Who have been the most influential and prolific authors across the five periods?
4. What country/regions have contributed most in the research across the five periods?

2.2 Methodology

For exploring the above-described research questions, we carry out the following procedures to collect and process data.

Methods for research topics

We downloaded all the abstracts of 5512 original articles from the basic corpus of this study by using a self-written R script to remove the garbled characters of the website. Since most research topics are nouns or noun phrases, we need to lemmatize and assign part of speech tags to the abstracts before extracting nouns. Then we use Treetagger, which is an automatic parts-of-speech tagging software developed by Helmut Schmid (1995) to annotate the abstracts with lemma information and part-of-speech. As for extracting n-grams from the part-of-speech, we employ AntConc, developed by Laurence Anthony (2023), which is a freeware corpus analysis tool for text analysis to extract monograms and n-grams of up to 3 words in length for the data from each of the five periods and the entire 45 years' data. And we filtered monograms and n-grams based on their frequency and range. Firstly, for the data from each of the five periods, we set a minimum frequency of 10, which is much lower than the threshold of 25 but this frequency matches the corpus size of five designated time periods to ensure that we can extract important themes. With the minimum frequency standard of 10 occurrences, our automatic search yielded a total of 7,097 n-grams (1363 monograms plus 5734 2-3 grams). Secondly, we removed all the 2-3 grams that ended or started with a function word (eg., of translation, translation of, in order to, translation as). Obviously, these phrases could not be research topics. However, some 2-3 grams with internal function words were reserved, such as translators and interpreters, role of translation and process of translation because they contributed to significant research topics. It is notable that when classifying and counting these n-grams, we group the singular and plural forms or different n-grams expressing the same meaning into the same category. For example, target text and target texts, as well as history of translation and translation history are all classified as one category.

With these filtering criteria, we retained 794 2-3 grams. Adding these to the 1363 monograms resulted in a total of 2157 n-grams to be meticulously examined. Finally, a total of 2157 n-grams were meticulously examined to determine their validity as research topics, as a considerable number of these n-grams did not reflect meaningful subjects within the field of translation studies. These non-research-topic items fell into three distinct categories. Firstly, there were concepts and issues that were excessively ubiquitous and broad within translation studies, lacking specific importance (e.g., language, features, differences, knowledge, conclusion, procedure, theory and practice). Secondly, there were commonly employed terminologies within language usage in general (e.g., analysis, process, development, and problems). Thirdly, those concepts and issues that are too common and universal in translation studies, rather than particularly important topics (e.g., translation and interpreting). It is imperative to concede that decisions within this sphere are inherently subjective, particularly in relation to the third category. The author has engaged in extensive deliberations with other scholars when making determinations regarding the third category. For instance, the complexity of factors involved and the ambiguity of certain criteria can make the decision-making process highly subjective. Another example could be that different scholars may have varying opinions and priorities when it comes to assessing projects in the third category. After extensive and in-depth discussions, it was determined which n-grams belong to the third category.

As discussed previously, the number of journal articles varied significantly across the five periods. In order to assess potential changes in the frequencies of candidate noun phrases over time, this study employed a normalized technique (Biber, Gray, and Poonpon 2011; Lan et al. 2022; Bao 2024) to analyze each type of noun phrases in each period. This involved dividing the frequency of a particular topic in each period by the total number of journal articles within that same period. Subsequently, to determine whether there were any notable differences in the frequency of topics across the five periods, a one-way Chi-square test was conducted. This test aimed to identify topics that experienced an increase in normalized frequency (referred to as "hot" topics) and those that displayed a decrease (referred to as "cold" topics). The following sections will present the hot/cold topics identified, along with the results of the one-way Chi-square tests.

Methods for the most highly cited articles

In order to identify the most highly-cited articles, we retrieved citation information for all the selected articles from Scopus.

Methods for the most influential and prolific authors

To assess the productivity of authors, we calculated the total number of publications by each author during each period. Concerning the determination of the most influential authors, we examined their H-index within each period.

Methods for identifying what country/regions have contributed most

We calculated the number of papers published by all authors in each country/region during each period.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 The Most Frequently-discussed Research Topics

Based on the above-mentioned research procedures and a manual selection, 57 most frequently discussed topics could be identified. Table 1 lists the frequently-explored research topics and their normalized frequencies across the five periods, including the P values and the Chi-squared of the statistical analysis for each.

These frequently-explored research topics and their respective Chi-square tests reveal some critical implications. These 57 topics fall into five groups. Group one (3 items) showed a continuous increase in frequency across the five periods. Group two (3 items) displayed a rise from period 1 to 2, a decline in period 3, but an increase from period 3 to period 5. Group three (22 items) exhibited a rise from period 1 to 2 or 3, a decline in period 3 or 4, but an increase from period 4 to period 5. Group four (2 items) showed a significant decline in frequency across the five periods. Group five (15 items) gained attention from period 1 to 2 or 3 or 4 period but have fallen by the wayside from period 3 or 4 to period 5. Group six (12 items) displayed no significant change across the five periods.

Considering brevity of discussion, we classify the Group 1, 2 and 3 as one group because these topics share a similarity of a rise across the five periods or an increase, at least, from period 3 to period 5, or from period 4 to period 5. This group, also the largest group, falls into six major categories: (i) those that are associated with interpreting studies, such as *cognitive load*, *consecutive interpreting*, *professional interpreters*, *notetaking*, and *student interpreters*. (ii) those that are either closely related to the development of computer and information, such as *translation technology*, *post-editing*, *machine translation*, *technology*, or related to multimodal translation, such as *subtitling*, *audiovisual translation*, *video* and *dubbing*. (iii) those that are distinctly associated with “the cultural turn” in translation, such as *identity*, *gender* and *ideology*. (iv) those that are possibly influenced by the paradigm of descriptive translation studies, such as *reception*, *reader*, *translator* and *interpreter*. (v) those that are either closely related to other disciplines’ theory or methodologies, such as *paratexts*, *corpus*, *discourse* and *eyetracking*. (vi) those that are traditional topics, including *literature*, *source text*, *literary translation*, *translation studies*.

Concerning the group four, only two items, including the translator’s voice and poetry, have demonstrated a significant decline across the five periods. Despite the importance of the translator’s voice as a research topic in translation studies, the most plausible explanation for its decline is that translation academia has shifted its focus towards more relevant topics such as *translator*, *interpreter*, *professional interpreters* and *student interpreters*, as well as other related fields.

Regarding the group five, there are 15 items that increased from period 1 to periods 2/3/4, but then decreased from periods 3/4 to 5. Some of these items, which were once popular in the 1989-1999 and 2000-2010 periods, include *equivalence* and *target text*. Most of this group is traditional topics such as *translation theory*, *history*, *translation process*, *situated learning* and *genre*. Other items in this group, which were expected to increase, such as *professional translators*, *simultaneous interpreting*, *interpreter training*, *translator education*, *translator training*, *community*, *legal translation* and *translation competence*, experienced a decrease from periods 3/4 to 5. Although there may be numerous reasons for the decrease, the most likely explanation is that periods 4 and 5 encompassed a shorter span of years compared to other periods. Alternatively, it could be that the translation circle has shifted their research focus to other topics.

In terms of the final group, the twelve items including *translation quality*, *interpreting students*, *localization*, *interpreting studies*, *sight translation*, *professional translation*, *news translation*, *court interpreting*, *translation history*, *copyright*, *audio description* and *corpus-based translation* did not exhibit significant changes in frequency across the five periods. Nevertheless, they remain crucial research topics in translation studies.

To better understand the shifts in research trends, we compared the results of this study with a previous study by Huang and Liu (2019), in order to identify both differences and similarities. Firstly, we highlight the discrepancies among them. The first difference is that certain topics, such as *cognitive load*, *eyetracking*, *post-editing*, *paratexts*, *reception*, *reader*, *gender*, *source text*, and *note-taking*, did not show high frequency between 2014-2018 in Huang and Liu’s (2019) study, but they have exhibited a remarkable increase throughout five periods, or an increase from Period 3 (2000-2010) to Period 4 (2011-2016) and Period 5 (2017-2022), or from Period 4 to Period 5. The second difference is that some topics, such as *translation theory*, *legal translation*, and *translation competence*, attracted great attention between 2014-2018 as shown in Huang and Liu’s (2019) study, but experienced a significant decline from period 3 or period 4 to period 5. The third difference is that some topics, such as *news translation*, *court interpreting*, *translation history*, *copyright*, *corpus-based translation* and *audio description* enjoyed high frequency between 2014-2018 in Huang and Liu’s (2019) study, but did not show significant changes in frequency across the five periods. The last difference is that some topics, such as *institutional translation*, *multilingualism*, and *retranslation*, were frequently explored between 2014-2018 but they did not belong to the significantly changing issues throughout the five periods of this study. There might be three reasons for these differences. The first reason is that topics are more likely to change significantly over 45 years than over 5 years. The second reason is that the sources of data for analysis: we extracted keywords from article abstracts in this study, while our previous study collected keywords from authors’ keywords. The third reason is that we adopted different

statistical approaches in two studies. In the previous study, we only calculated the frequency of the keywords, while in the latter study, we employed a normalization technique and conducted a one-way Chi-square test to determine whether there were any notable differences in the frequency of topics across the five periods.

Regarding similarities, firstly, it is notable that both our previous study and this one have indicated a decline in the research interest in certain traditional topics, for instance, *equivalence*, *poetry*, and *translation process*. Secondly, both the previous and the current study have discovered a substantial increase in the frequency of terms related to *new technology*, *audiovisual translation*, *subtitling*, *machine translation*, and *corpus*. Thirdly, the two studies have also exposed a continuous research interest in some traditional topics, namely *literature*, *discourse*, *literary translation*, and *ideology*. There might be some reasons for these similarities, in the case of the decline in traditional topics, such as poetry, it is likely that the focus has shifted away. This might be attributed to changing societal preferences and educational priorities. For instance, in a society that increasingly values practical and applied knowledge, areas like poetry, which are seen as more aesthetic and less directly applicable, may receive less attention. Regarding the increase in new technology-related terms, the rapid advancement of digital tools and the growing significance of global communication are likely the driving forces. Take the example of *machine translation*: as international business and cultural exchanges expand, the demand for efficient translation solutions powered by technology has soared. As for the continuous interest in traditional topics like *literature*, it could be because of their enduring cultural significance and complexity. Literature often reflects the essence of human experiences and emotions across different eras, and its complexity offers endless opportunities for in-depth exploration and interpretation, which continues to captivate researchers.

Table_1: Topics with Increased and Decreased Normalized Frequency

Topics	Normalized Frequency 1978-1988	Normalized Frequency 1989-1999	Normalized Frequency 2000-2010	Normalized Frequency 2011-2016	Normalized Frequency 2017-2022	Chi-square	P-Value
Group one: significantly increased							
cognitive load	0.00	0.00	0.27	0.40	1.89	13.99	0.00
translation technology	0.00	0.21	0.27	0.50	2.21	16.55	0.00
eyetracking	0.00	0.00	0.40	0.40	1.10	4.36	0.04
Group two: increased from period 1 to 2 , declined in period 3, but increased from period 3 to period 5							
postediting	0.00	0.84	0.14	1.34	6.10	47.20	0.00
machine translation	0.00	2.10	1.90	3.15	6.36	17.62	0.00
paratexts	0.00	0.63	0.14	0.34	2.63	26.15	0.00
Group three: increased from period 1 to 2/ 3, declined in period 3/4, but increased from period 4 to period 5							
corpus	0.00	6.33	23.36	10.60	15.46	16.67	0.00
identity	0.00	1.27	3.25	0.34	1.10	5.52	0.02
translator	38.55	90.72	93.77	30.78	37.54	16.58	0.00
interpreter	2.79	53.38	39.61	18.85	31.97	73.73	0.00
translation studies	0.00	2.74	26.47	7.18	9.20	4.23	0.04
literature	5.59	11.39	18.96	4.29	6.10	5.08	0.02
discourse	0.56	14.56	15.17	2.48	4.89	12.51	0.00
subtitling	0.00	3.59	4.60	3.35	7.10	22.01	0.00
technology	0.00	0.21	5.35	1.81	5.73	32.37	0.00
reception	0.00	3.16	3.32	1.34	4.31	24.27	0.00
reader	0.56	13.29	12.12	1.27	2.58	6.57	0.01
gender	0.00	0.42	1.35	0.34	2.00	17.16	0.00
consecutive interpreting	0.00	0.63	1.42	0.80	1.84	5.82	0.02
source text	0.00	17.72	33.92	3.82	5.89	7.10	0.01
ideology	0.00	2.95	4.60	0.20	1.37	12.06	0.00
audiovisual translation	0.00	0.42	4.60	1.95	3.31	5.42	0.02
video	0.00	0.00	0.61	0.27	2.10	20.57	0.00
literary translation	3.35	4.01	6.23	0.13	1.37	14.05	0.00
professional interpreters	0.00	1.27	1.49	0.47	1.31	5.51	0.02
notetaking	0.00	0.00	0.81	0.07	1.05	11.62	0.00
student interpreters	0.00	0.21	0.68	0.34	1.42	9.39	0.00
dubbing	0.00	2.74	3.25	0.47	2.42	19.40	0.00
Group four: significantly decreased							
translators voice	24.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	121.05	0.00

poetry	5.03	5.49	2.57	0.07	0.53	59.26	0.00
Group five: increased from period 1 to period 2/3/4, but declined from period 3/4 to period 5							
translation theory	1.68	12.24	5.01	0.54	0.47	187.32	0.00
equivalence	0.00	11.81	10.29	0.54	0.42	183.61	0.00
target text	0.00	12.24	29.86	3.09	2.79	73.98	0.00
history	0.00	9.70	8.53	2.48	1.84	68.90	0.00
translation process	0.00	5.91	11.58	5.97	4.10	66.99	0.00
professional translator	0.00	1.90	4.67	2.95	1.37	32.03	0.00
simultaneous interpreting	0.00	3.59	5.08	2.35	1.52	34.00	0.00
genre	0.00	6.75	4.60	2.55	1.37	43.95	0.00
interpreter training	0.56	0.63	1.69	3.09	0.99	18.27	0.00
situated learning	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.61	0.16	20.52	0.00
translator education	0.00	0.00	0.54	1.54	0.74	4.32	0.04
translator training	0.00	0.63	8.40	2.21	1.47	91.15	0.00
community	0.56	2.95	7.18	4.56	4.10	14.68	0.00
legal translation	0.00	0.63	1.62	0.67	0.37	13.10	0.00
translation competence	0.00	1.05	2.57	0.87	0.84	14.77	0.00
Group six: remain unchanged							
translation quality	0.00	0.42	1.49	0.67	1.31	2.79	0.09
interpreting students	0.00	0.00	0.95	1.48	0.84	2.49	0.11
localisation	0.00	0.00	2.98	1.14	2.10	2.28	0.13
interpreting studies	0.00	0.42	0.88	0.54	1.21	2.67	0.10
sight translation	0.00	0.00	0.61	0.74	1.00	0.39	0.53
professional translation	0.00	0.00	0.68	0.40	0.53	0.07	0.79
news translation	0.00	0.63	0.74	0.54	0.63	0.02	0.90
court interpreting	0.00	0.63	0.41	0.20	0.16	0.01	0.91
translation history	0.00	0.42	0.88	0.54	0.58	0.00	0.94
copyright	0.00	0.42	0.74	0.40	0.79	1.45	0.23
audio description	0.00	0.00	1.22	1.27	0.74	1.99	0.16
corpus-based translation	0.00	0.00	0.27	0.00	0.32	3.09	0.08

3.2 The Highly-Cited Articles across the five periods

We have identified the top ten most highly-cited articles in each of the five periods covered in Table 2. It is worth noting that the research issues discussed in these highly-cited articles coincide with the most frequently-discussed topics identified in Table 1. For instance, the surveyed issues in articles such as “Resistance and accommodation: factors for the (non-) adoption of machine translation among professional translators,” “Corpora in translation studies: An overview and some suggestions for future research,” “FanSuBS: Audiovisual translation in an amateur environment,” “ ‘Subtitling’s a carnival’: New practices in cyberspace Jorge Diaz Cintas, University College London,” and “Cognitive load in simultaneous interpreting: Existing theories - New models” correlate to the high-frequency topics related to computer development, including machine translation and corpus. Moreover, these articles also touch on cognitive load and multimodal translation topics such as subtitling and audiovisual translation. Interestingly, five articles associated with machine translation appear in the top ten most highly-cited articles from 2017 to 2022. This trend highlights the growing importance of machine translation in the field of translation studies.

Table_2: Samples of Highly-Cited Articles

No.	1978-1988			1989-1999			2000-2010			2011-2016			2017-2022		
	Title	Author	Citation Frequency	Title	Author	Citation Frequency	Title	Author	Citation Frequency	Title	Author	Citation Frequency	Title	Author	Citation Frequency
1	The translation of metaphor	Newmark, Peter	26	Corpora in translation studies: An	Baker, M.	435	Towards a methodology for investi	Baker, M.	247	Translation and mass-communication: Film	Delabastita, D.	193	Resistance and accommodation: factors	Cadwell, P., O'Brien, S.	71

				overview and some suggestions for future research			gating the style of a literary translator			and t.v. translation as evidence of cultural dynamics			for the (non-) adoption of machine translation among professional translators	Teixeira, C.S.C.	
2	A woman in translation, reflecting	Maier, Carol S.	22	The pivotal status of the translator's Habitus	Simoni, D.	359	Translation techniques revisited: A dynamic and functionalist approach	Molina, L., Albir, A.H.	238	Cognitive load in simultaneous interpreting: Existing theories - New models	Seeber, K.G.	113	Under pressure: translation in times of austerity	Moorrens, J.	59
3	Metaphor and translation		22	The translator's voice in translated narrative	Hermans, T	199	Investigating translation competence: Conceptual and methodological issues	Bebey, A., Fernández, M., Fox, O., ... Romero, L., Albir, A.H.	207	Situated learning in translator and interpreter training: Bridging research and good practice	González-Davies, M., Enríquez-Raído, V.	100	Conducting experimental research in audiovisual translation (AVT): A position paper	Orero, P., Doherty, S., Kruger, J.-L., ... Soler-Vilageliu, O., Szarkowska, A.	58
4	The inescapable dilemma quality and/or quantity in interpreting		12	Translation and original similarities and dissimilarities	Van Leuven-Zwar, K.M.	151	Redefining translation competence in an electronic age. In defence of a minimalist approach	Pym, A.	203	What technology does to translation	Pym, A.	98	Theoretical, methodological and terminological issues regarding indirect translation: an overview	Rosa, A., Pięta, H., Bueno Maia, R.	58
5	Translating comic writing		10	From 'Is' to 'ought': Laws, norms and strategies in translation studies	Chesterman, A.	140	FanSubS: Audiovisual translation in an amateur environment	Cintas, J.D., Sánchez, P.M.	201	Evaluating emotional stability as a predictor of interpreter competence and aptitude	Bontempo, K., Napier, J.	98	Machine translation and post-editing training as part of a master's programme	Arenas, A. G., Moorrens, J.	55

										for interpreting					
6	Translation theory : A challenge for the future		8	The bilingual individual	Grosjean, F.	118	Translation and political engagement: Activism, social change and the role of translation in geopolitical shifts	Tymoczko, M.	196	Fifteen years of journalistic translation research and more	Valdeón, R. A.	93	What to expect from neural machine translation: a practical in-class translation evaluation exercise	Moorrens, J.	53
7	Back-translation to recover form		7	The concept of equivalence and the object of translation studies	Koller, W.	113	Habitus, field and discourse: Interpreting as a socially situated activity	Inghilleri, M.	194	Language variation in source texts and their translations: the case of L3 in film translation	Corrius, M., Zabalbascoa, P.	89	Quality assessment in interlingual live subtitling: the NTR model	Romero-Fresco, P., Pöchhacker, F.	52
8	Translation as performance : Three notes		7	There is always a teller in a tale	Schiavi, G.	111	Unexpected allies: How Latour's network theory could complement Bourdieusian analyses in translation studies	Buzelin, H.	164	Translators and translation technology: the dance of agency	Olohan, M.	84	Translators and machine translation: knowledge and skills gaps in translation pedagogy	Mellinger, C.D.	51
9	On not reviewing translations: A critical exchange		7	The moral dilemmas of court interpreting	Morris, R.	109	Epistemicide! : the tale of a predatory discourse	Bennett, K.	148	Ethics in interpreter & translation training : critical perspectives	Baker, M., Maier, C.	82	The impact of google neural machine translation on post-editing by student translators	Yamada, M.	47
10	The translator's voice: An		7	Scopos, loyalty and translation	Nord, C.	104	Interpreting in asylum hearing	Pöllabauer, S.	149	A survey of machine	Gaspari, F., Almaghout, H.,	78	'Subtitling's a carnival': New	Díaz Cintas, J.	47

interview with Gregory Rabassa			ditional conventions			s: Issues of role, responsibility and power			translation competences: insights of translation technology educators and practitioners	Doherty, S.		practices in cyberspace Jorge Díaz Cintas, University College London		
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3.3 The Most Productive and Highly Influential Authors

It is widely known that the H-index and scholarly output are used to assess scholars’ academic competence and productivity. To identify the most productive and highly influential authors, we investigated their scholarly output and H-index in each period, as reported in Table 3. The first finding is that, in terms of scholarly output, Schulte published 11, 10, and 14 articles in the first (1978-1988), second (1989-1999), and third (2000-2010) periods, respectively, ranking first. Pym published 12 articles in the fourth period (2011-2016) and Valdeón published 16 articles in the fifth period (2017-2022), both ranking first in their respective periods. These most productive authors are mainly engaged in translation theory, translation and literary criticism, the translator’s voice, and literary translation (e.g., R. Schulte), translation competence, explicitation, simultaneous interpreting, the translator, and sight translation (e.g., A. Pym), news translation, the interpreter, translator, subtitling, audiovisual translation, and dubbing (e.g., R.A.Valdeón).

The second result is that Schulte, Newmark, and Maier had the highest H-index of 3 in the first period. Shlesinger and Nord had the highest H-index of 6 in the second period. Pöchhacker boasted of the highest H-index of 14 in the third period, followed closely by Pym, Orero, Zethsen, and Tymoczko with H-index of 13, 12, 11, and 10, respectively. Pym and Napier possessed the highest H-index of 11 in the fourth period, followed by Koskinen with H-index of 10. Szarkowska boasted of the highest H-index of 17 in the fifth period, followed closely by Napier with an H-index of 11. For the sake of brevity, we only focus on highly influential authors with an H-index of 10 or above. The research focus of these authors included simultaneous interpreting, translator, sight translation (e.g., F. Pöchhacker), audio description (e.g., P. Orero), the unified medical language system (e.g., K.K. Zethsen), the evolution of language, artificial grammar learning, cultural relativism (e.g., M. Tymoczko), simultaneous interpreting, translator, sight translation (e.g., J. Napier), retranslation, paratext, literary translation (e.g., K. Koskinen), and listening comprehension, EFL Learner, subtitling, audiovisual translation, dubbing, cognitive load, eye-tracking technology (e.g., A. Szarkowska).

The last finding is that although Baker and Simeoni only published 6 and 5 articles, respectively, with H-index of 20 and 5, respectively, Baker’s article “Corpora in Translation Studies: An Overview and Some Suggestions for Future Research” became the most highly cited paper, and Simeoni’s article “The Pivotal Status of the Translator’s Habitus” was the second most highly cited paper across the five periods, with 435 and 360 citations, respectively. It is also worth mentioning that Baker’s article “Towards a Methodology for Investigating the Style of a Literary Translator” was the third most cited paper across the five periods, with 248 citations. It is clear that Baker’s research interests reflected in these two articles centered on corpus-based translation studies. Furthermore, Baker’s classic book, Translation and Conflict: A Narrative Account, delves into the role of translators and interpreters in violent conflicts through the lens of narrative theory and has received 800 citations. This work also intersects with intercultural studies, politics, and sociology.

The publication and citation details of Baker have been highlighted. Despite the relatively small number of articles published by Baker, her works have achieved significant citation counts. As is evident from the highly cited articles and the book, Baker’s research interests focus on corpus-based translation studies and have intersections with multiple disciplines. This clearly indicates Baker’s prominent position and influence in the field of translation studies.

Table_3: Samples of Most Productive Authors

No.	1978-1988			1989-1999			2000-2010			2011-2016			2017-2022		
	Author	No. Of Article	H-index												

1	Schulte, R.	11	H-3	Schulte, R.	10	H-1	Schulte, R.	14	H-2	Pym, A.	12	H-11	Valdeón, R.A.	16	H-6
2	Kratz, D.	4	H-1	Shlesinger, M.	6	H-6	Pym, A.	9	H-13	Washbourne, K.	10	H-4	Olalla-Soler, C.	14	H-9
3	Simpson, E.	3	H-2	Weissbrod, R.	4	H-3	Orero, P.	9	H-12	Valdeón, R.A.	9	H-9	Han, C.	12	H-9
4	Newmark, P.	3	H-3	Pym, A.	4	H-5	Zethsen, K.K.	8	H-11	Matamala, A.	9	H-9	Zheng, B.	11	H-6
5	Mann, P.	3	H-1	Ballard, M.	4	H-2	Li, D.	8	H-8	Jiménez-Crespo, M.A.	9	H-2	Mellinger, C.D.	11	H-9
6	Maier, C.	3	H-3	Wilss, W.	3	H-5	Zhong, Y.	7	H-5	Napier, J.	7	H-11	Defrancq, B.	11	H-7
7	Hoeksema, T.	3	H-1	Vermeer, H.J.	3	H-4	Waldinger, A.	7	H-2	Lee, T.K.	7	H-5	Szarkowska, A.	10	H-17
8	Scharnhorst, G.	2	H-1	Sidiropoulou, M.	3	H-5	Pöchhacker, F.	7	H-14	Koskinen, K.	7	H-10	Remael, A.	8	H-7
9	Raffel, B.	2	H-1	Schäffner, C.	3	H-5	Gillespie, S.	7	H-7	Schäffner, C.	6	H-9	Pym, A.	8	H-8
10	Nida, E.A.	2	H-1	Nord, C.	3	H-6	Tymoczko, M.	6	H-10	Remael, A.	6	H-9	Napier, J.	8	H-11

3.4 Most Productive Countries and Territories

Table 4 reports the 10 countries/regions that contributed the most in each period, as well as the number of articles from each country/region and the percentage of articles in total published in that period. The reason for including percentage data is that, as mentioned earlier, the total number of articles published in these periods varies greatly, so comparing raw data would be invalid. A careful examination found that due to historical reasons and the fact that international translation journals basically require publication in English, western countries and regions such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia, and European countries have consistently comprised the majority of the top contributing countries over the past 45 years, but the number of western countries/regions has actually decreased, while the number of non-western countries/regions has increased. For example, the number of non-western countries/regions among the top 5 contributors increased from 0 in the first and second period to 2 in the third period and 1 in the fourth and fifth phases.

In addition, China, as one of non-western countries, has seen an increase in its ranking due to a significant increase in the number of articles it has published. As reported in Table 4, China rose from 8th in the first period to 6th in the second period, 4th in the third and fourth periods, and 2nd in the fifth period. The most conclusive evidence of the significant increase in contributions from non-western countries/regions is the significant increase in the percentage of publications they account for in each period. For example, in the first phase, the three non-western countries/regions (China, Iraq and Nigeria) among the top 10 contributors published only 1.68% of the total number of publications in the same period. In the second phase, the percentage of the three non-western countries/regions (China, Hong Kong and Israel) among the top 10 contributing countries rose to 13.5%, eight times that of the first phase. Then, in the third and fourth phases, the proportion of articles published by the two non-western countries/regions (China and Hong Kong) among the top 10 contributing countries slightly decreased, but still remained at a relatively high level, at 9.61% and 10.46% respectively in these two periods. In the fifth phase, the percentage of articles published by the two non-western countries/regions (China and Hong Kong) among the top 10 contributing countries rose to 17.41%.

However, it should be emphasized that despite the substantial surge in the total number of publications from non-western countries/regions, this growth is primarily attributed to a handful of Asian nations/territories, namely China and Hong Kong. In contrast, African and Central/South American countries/regions contribute sparsely to academic literature. To foster academic collaboration and development across diverse regions, it is recommended that international translation journals actively seek contributions from these two continents, thereby ensuring a more comprehensive representation of developing countries/regions in academic discourse.

Table_4: Samples of Most Countries and Territories

No.	1978-1988			1989-1999			2000-2010			2011-2016			2017-2022		
	Country	No. Of Article	%												
1	United States	82	45.81 %	United States	92	19.41 %	Spain	199	13.47 %	Spain	226	15.16 %	United Kingdom	305	16.04 %
2	Canada	4	2.23 %	United Kingdom	72	15.19 %	United Kingdom	170	11.51 %	United Kingdom	206	13.82 %	China	266	13.99 %
3	United Kingdom	3	1.68 %	Spain	32	6.75 %	United States	99	6.70 %	United States	181	12.14 %	Spain	223	11.72 %
4	Germany	2	1.12 %	Germany	31	6.54 %	China	77	5.21 %	China	94	6.30 %	United States	154	8.10 %
5	Poland	1	0.56 %	Canada	24	5.06 %	Hong Kong	65	4.40 %	Australia	83	5.57 %	Belgium	86	4.52 %
6	Nigeria	1	0.56 %	China	23	4.85 %	Canada	56	3.79 %	Belgium	68	4.56 %	Australia	82	4.31 %
7	Italy	1	0.56 %	Israel	21	4.43 %	Denmark	55	3.72 %	Hong Kong	62	4.16 %	Poland	73	3.84 %
8	China	1	0.56 %	Hong Kong	20	4.22 %	Belgium	54	3.66 %	Italy	58	3.89 %	Italy	71	3.73 %
9	Iraq	1	0.56 %	Finland	16	3.38 %	Australia	51	3.45 %	Canada	58	3.89 %	Hong Kong	65	3.42 %
10	Hungary	1	0.56 %	Belgium	16	3.38 %	Italy	48	3.25 %	Finland	37	2.48 %	Canada	55	2.89 %

4. Conclusion

Through a bibliometric analysis of articles published in 14 international translation journals indexed in the SSCI or A&HCI databases from 1978 to 2022, this study identifies a diverse range of insights, including the most frequently explored topics over the past 45 years, their evolving trends across five distinct periods, the most highly-cited articles, the most productive and influential authors, and the most productive countries and territories.

The implications of this study can be summarized as follows. Firstly, topics related to technological advancements and multimodal translation, such as *translation technology*, *post-editing*, *machine translation*, *subtitling* and *audiovisual translation* (see Table 1) are increasingly prevalent. This highlights how emerging technologies are reshaping the field of translation studies. Secondly, the lasting impact of the cultural turn is evident through the continued prominence of topics such as *identity*, *gender* and *ideology* (see Table 1).

Thirdly, it is well known that descriptive translation studies (DTS), firstly put forward by Holmes (1988), aim to describe and explain translation phenomena comprehensively and objectively, focusing on translation norms, translation behaviors and processes (translators, translator's strategies etc.), translation products (linguistic features of translated texts), and factors influencing translation (reception, readers, etc.). As shown in Table 1, current translation studies are still influenced by the paradigm of descriptive translation studies, which can be seen from the continued significant importance of some topics, such as *translators*, *interpreter*, *reader* and *reception*.

Fourthly, traditional subjects like *literature*, *source texts*, *literary translation* and *translation studies* (see Table 1) remain significant areas of research. Fifthly, there has been a shift in research focus. Some previously popular topics, including *translation theory*, *equivalence*, *target text*, *history*, *translation process*, *professional translator*, *simultaneous interpreting*, *genre*, *interpreting training*, *situated learning*, *translator education*, *translator training*, *community*, *legal translation* and *translation competence* (see Table 1), have declined in prominence from periods 3/4 to period 5. This shift may reflect a transition in research focus and the emergence of new fields.

Sixthly, interdisciplinary studies are receiving growing attention, as could be witnessed by the increasing frequency of keywords such as *discourse* and *corpus* that originate from discourse analysis and corpus studies in linguistics. Moreover, the interdisciplinary phenomenon in translation could also be perceived from the significant increase of the term *eyetracking* across the five periods (see Table 1). Initially applied in psychology, eyetracking research has provided insights into cognitive processes, attention allocation, and information processing. Over the past five periods, translation scholars have increasingly embarked on exploring the attention allocation of translators during the translation process from the perspective of eyetracking, including its application in sight translation studies. Additionally, the adoption of interdisciplinary approaches in translation studies is further supported by the fluctuation in the keyword *paratexts*, which increased from periods 1 to 2, declined in period 3, and then rose again from period 3 to period 5 (see Table 1). Originally a literary concept, paratexts include elements such as covers, titles, prefaces, postscripts, annotations, and illustrations, offering valuable background information for translation studies. For instance, translators' prefaces and postscripts could reveal translators' motivations, strategies, and interpretations of the original work. Consequently, an increasing number of scholars are exploring translation studies from the perspective of paratexts. This indicates the need for researchers to keep pace with developments in the field and explore new research directions.

Finally, it is important to recognize that although the frequency of some topics remains relatively stable, they continue to be crucial in translation studies. Topics such as *translation quality*, *interpreting students*, *localization*, *sight translation*, *professional translation*, *news translation*, *court interpreting*, *history of translation*, *censorship*, *audio description* and *corpus-based translation* (see Table 1) remain vital.

This study utilizes bibliometric and cross-period comparison approaches to offer a comprehensive overview of research dynamics within the field and provide implications for future studies. However, as this bibliometric study involves qualitative data analysis, some degree of subjectivity in interpreting the corpora and drawing conclusions is inevitable. Future research could enhance validity and reliability by incorporating methods such as surveys and interviews.

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